

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№10

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2025

oktyabr

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 – Texnika fanlari
08.00.00 – Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB™
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic
Resource
Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ
БИБЛИОТЕКА
LIBRARY.RU

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 363 sahifa.
2025-yil, 18-oktyabr,

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afrovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Muhammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

JAHON MOLIYA TIZIMIDA “YASHIL” MOLIYALASHTIRISHNI RIVOJLANISHINING MUAMMOLARI VA SHARTLARI	12
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
EKOLOGIK MIGRANTSIYANI MINTAQAVIY MIQYOSDA MUVOFIQLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI	18
Bahtiyor Ismoilov Ulug‘bek o‘g‘li, Kadirova Zulayxo Abduxalimovna	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA BANK XIZMATLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH HOLATI	25
Davletova Nilufar Tulanovna	
EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHDA MINTAQANI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA‘SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	30
Qodirov Farrux Ergash o‘g‘li	
SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI	37
Kadirxodjayeva Nilufar Raxmatullayevna	
MAHALLIY XOMASHYO BAZASIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI ISHLAB CHIQARISH XARAJATLARINI KAMAYTIRISH YO‘LLARI	46
Sultanov Dilshod Normamatovich	
IQTISODIYOTI RIVOJLANGAN DAVLATLARDA INSON KAPITALIGA INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB QILISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	50
Akhmadaliyeva Nikholakhon	
O‘QITUVCHILAR VA TALABALAR UCHUN INNOVATSION TA‘LIM DASTURLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISHDA XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MOSLASHUV MEXANIZMLARI	62
Yuldashev Iskandar Bahromovich	
YER QA‘RIDAN FOYDALANGANLIK UCHUN SOLIQLARNING ILMIY-TADQIQOTLAR SHARHI	68
Zoxidov Ismatjon Yunusjon o‘g‘li	
RESPUBLIKA IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTIDA OLIY TA‘LIMNI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH VA INVESTITSIYA JOZIBADORLIGINING O‘RNI	74
Jonuzokov Mirzabek Kulmamatovich	
DAVLAT IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASHDA SIYOSIY INSTITUTLARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	80
O. Nurmuradov	
ICHKI AUDIT SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA BUXGALTERIYA MA‘LUMOTLARINING ICHKI AUDIT JARAYONIDA EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	85
Xamidov Javoxir Shavkat o‘g‘li, Muxitdinov Shoxijaxon Xudoyor o‘g‘li	
XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB ETISHNING MOLIYAVIY MEXANIZMLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	90
Xuramov Zafar Rajabaliyevich	
KORPORATIV TUZILMALARDA INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKNI TA‘MINLASHNING AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISHDAGI ROLI	95
Qurbonov Javlonbek Jurabekovich, Raxmatov Faxriddin Xasanovich	
GLOBAL RIVOJLANISH JARAYONIDA SUG‘URTA XIZMATLARINI ISLOH QILISH MASALALARI	99
Xushmuradov Oman, Ismoilov Sherzod Ismoil o‘g‘li	

DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	103
Usmonov Mirg'ulom Xoshim o'g'li	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHGA ERISHISHDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TIZIMLARINI QO'LLASH METODOLOGIYASINING AHAMIYATI	109
Nasrulloev Hayotjon Xabibulloevich	
НЕЙРОИНТУИТИВНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ КАК ФАКТОР КОНКУРЕНТНОГО ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА НА РЫНКЕ ТРУДА.....	115
Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович	
RESURSLARNI SOLIQQA TORTISHGA OID TADQIQOTLARNING NAZARIY TAHLILI.....	123
Nasimdjanoov Yunusjon Zoxidovich	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR FAOLIYATINI MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH: XULQ-ATVOR IQTISODIYOTI VA PROGRESSIV TARIFLARNI LOYIHALASH	129
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
DAVLAT RAQAMLI LOYIHALARI: UZINFOCOMNING TA'LIM TIZIMI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA QO'SHGAN HISSASI	134
Raxmatxo'jayev Axrorxo'ja Akmal o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ПАСПОРТОВ В ПРОМЫШЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ И ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ.....	140
Мансурова Сайёра Бахтияровна	
BANK XIZMATLARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	148
Xolikova Oydin Olimjonovna	
PNEVMOMEXANIK YIGIRISH TEXNOLOGIYASI XUSUSIYATLARI	153
Jumaniyazov Kadam, Salimov Shuhrat Halimovich, Nazarov Ramazon Anvarovich	
GREEN INDUSTRY AND THE ECONOMY OF ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY CONSTRUCTION: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND UZBEKISTAN'S OPPORTUNITIES.....	158
Mansurova Sayyora Bakhtiyor kizi	
TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TAHLILI	166
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINING MIKRO VA MAKRO TUZILMALARI, ULARNING FUNKSIONAL METADOLOGIK TAMOYILLARI.....	171
Z.Teshayev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT ULUSHI MAVJUD KORXONALARNI BOSHQARISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBADAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	176
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
MAHSULOT TANNARXINI ANIQLASHDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARJATLARINI OG'ISHISHLARI VA ULARNI TAQSIMLASH	183
Raxmatov Baxriddin Baxtiyor o'g'li	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ СТОИМОСТИ СПОРТИВНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ И ОБЪЕКТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ АУТСОРСИНГА	186
Исмагулова Гульмира Нуралиевна	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYASI.....	193
Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING INSTITUTSIONAL VA TASHKILYIY MEXANIZMLARI.....	198
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA UZOQ MUDDATLI RESURSLARNI JALB QILISHDA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	203
Abduraxmonov Akmal Nurmat o'g'li	

MEHNATGA LAYOQATLI TRANSPORT SOHASIDAGI AHOLINI ISH O'RINLARI BILAN TA'MINLANGANLIK HOLATINI TAHLILI	207
Abdullayeva Nigora Shamsiddinovna	
TO'QIMACHILIK SOHASINI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISH MODELI	212
Mdraximova Gulasal Ro'zimboy qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT PORTFELI DIVERSIFIKATSIIYASI VA GAROV TA'MINOTI SIFATINING BANK BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRI	220
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON - 2030 STRATEGIYASI DOIRASIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	226
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XIZMATLARNI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KLASTERLI MEXANIZMI TAHLILI	232
Odamboyev Oybek Ravshanbek o'g'li	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TUZILMALARIDA MOLIYAVIY MUNOSABATLARNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI	236
Qurbaniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich	
XALQARO SAVDONING RIVOJLANISHI VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	242
Jalolov Bekzod Sherzod o'g'li	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING YANGI TIZIMINI JORIY ETISHGA QARATILGAN NAZARIY JIHATLAR	247
Dusanov Salim Mamarasulovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA BOJXONA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	254
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
DAVLAT TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA QURILISH XARAJATLARI HISOBINI YURITISH	262
Ostonokulov Azamat Abdugarimovich	
РАЗРАБОТКА ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ КРЕАТИВНЫХ ИНДУСТРИЙ В ТУРИСТИЧЕСКУЮ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН	273
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
A NEW STAGE IN THE APPLICATION OF MARKET MECHANISMS TO ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY	285
Ibrayim Maxkamov	
RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH ORQALI SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH XIZMATLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI	291
Eshbekova Xayriniso Baxtiyorovna	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI IQTISODIYOTIDA DXSH ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITINING SHAKLLANISHI	297
Hamroyev G'ayratjon Sultonovich	
TURIZM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJLARINI O'RGANISH VA TAHLIL QILISH	301
Shaymanov To'lqin Mahmayusupovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И ЦИФРОВЫХ ПОДХОДОВ В НАЛОГОВОМ ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВЕ	306
Элбаева Мукаддас Рашидовна	
СИНТЕЗ НЕЧЕТКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕПЛОЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ ОБЪЕКТОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ	311
Бахриева Хуршида Аскарходжаевна, Сафаров Шохрух Шарофович, Бахрамов Муҳаммадали Ералиевичасистент	
ШАНХАЙСКАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА КАК КАТАЛИЗАТОР ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕЛЕЙ РАЗВИТИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	319
Базарова Гулнара Гуламовна	

O'ZBEKISTON KORXONALARINING TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA BANK KREDITLASH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	323
Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
QUESTIONS ABOUT THE STUDY OF PERFORMANCE AND EFFICIENCY OF APPLICATION OF LOADING AND EXTRACTING EQUIPMENT	327
Azamat Umirzokov	
MATOLARNING HAVO O'TKAZUVCHANLIGI KORRELATSION TAHLILI.....	334
Ismailov Nurulla Tuychibayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI RISKLARINI SUG'URTALASHNING AFZALLIKLARI	339
Mamadjanov Shuxrat Jalolidinovich	
IKKI QATLAMLI ARALASH TOLA TARKIBLI TRIKOTAJ TO'QIMASINI OLIQ USULI	343
Usnatdinova Elmira Faxratdinovna, Mirusmanov Baxtiyor, Abdurahimova Fazilat Abdullayevna	
MAHALLIY DAVLAT HOKIMIYATI ORGANLARIDA ENG ILG'OR TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONLARINING OPTIMALLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	347
Axmedov Farxod Raxmonjonovich	
IMPACT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS ON THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN: CROSS-SECTORAL ANALYSIS.....	354
Jumayeva Kamola Azimjonovna, Khasanova Iroda Azizbek kizi	

IMPACT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS ON THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN: CROSS-SECTORAL ANALYSIS

Jumayeva Kamola Azimjonovna

Master's student of Tashkent State
University of Economics
comowii.19@gmail.com

Khasanova Iroda Azizbek kizi

Master's student of Tashkent State
University of Economics
xasanova.iroda20@gmail.com

Abstract. Foreign direct investment (FDI) plays a vital role in enhancing economic growth by transferring capital, technologies, and management practices into host economies. This paper examines the cross-sectoral impact of FDI on Uzbekistan's economy by focusing on agriculture, industry, and services. Using time-series data from 1997 to 2023, we analyze trends, patterns, and sectoral performance indicators such as output, employment, and growth rates. While many studies concentrate on the aggregate effect of FDI on GDP, our research introduces novelty by conducting a sector-specific analysis. The findings highlight that foreign investments have significantly contributed to industrial development and the expansion of the service sector, particularly in transportation, logistics, tourism, and ICT. At the same time, agriculture has shown moderate but stable growth from FDI inflows. Econometric results confirm that FDI positively correlates with sectoral employment and output, though the magnitude differs across sectors. This study provides empirical evidence and practical recommendations for policymakers to optimize sector-targeted investment strategies and strengthen Uzbekistan's long-term economic development.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), economic growth, Uzbekistan, agriculture, industry, services, sectoral analysis, employment, GDP, cross-sectoral impact.

Annotatsiya. To'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar (TXI) kapital, texnologiyalar va boshqaruv tajribasini qabul qiluvchi mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga olib kirish orqali iqtisodiy o'sishni rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqola O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida TXIning qishloq xo'jaligi, sanoat va xizmat ko'rsatish sohaslariga kesimdagi ta'sirini o'rganadi. 1997–2023-yillar davrini qamrab olgan vaqt qatori ma'lumotlari asosida TXI oqimlari, ularning dinamikasi va tarmoqlar samaradorligi ko'rsatkichlari jumladan, ishlab chiqarish hajmi, bandlik va o'sish sur'atlari tahlil qilinadi. Aksariyat tadqiqotlar TXIning umumiy YaIMga ta'siriga e'tibor qaratgan bo'lsa, bizning tadqiqotimiz yangilik sifatida tarmoqlar kesimidagi tahlilni taqdim etadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, xorijiy investitsiyalar sanoat rivojiga va xizmatlar sektorining kengayishiga sezilarli hissa qo'shgan, xususan, transport-logistika, turizm va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari sohaslarida. Shu bilan birga, qishloq xo'jaligida TXI oqimlari barqaror, biroq o'rtacha darajada o'sishni ta'minlagan. Ekonometriya natijalari TXIning bandlik va ishlab chiqarish ko'rsatkichlari bilan ijobiy korrelyatsiyasini tasdiqlaydi, ammo ta'sir kuchi sohaslar kesimida farq qiladi. Tadqiqot O'zbekistonning uzoq muddatli iqtisodiy rivojlanishini ta'minlashda tarmoqlar bo'yicha investitsiya siyosatini takomillashtirish uchun amaliy tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: To'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar (TXI), iqtisodiy o'sish, O'zbekiston, qishloq xo'jaligi, sanoat; xizmatlar sohasi, tarmoqlararo tahlil, bandlike, YaIM, kesimiy ta'sir.

Аннотация. Прямые иностранные инвестиции (ПИИ) играют важную роль в стимулировании экономического роста за счет привлечения капитала, технологий и управленческого опыта в принимающие экономики. В данной статье рассматривается межотраслевая роль ПИИ в экономике Узбекистана с акцентом на сельское хозяйство, промышленность и сферу услуг. На основе временных рядов за 1997–2023 годы проведён анализ динамики, тенденций и показателей эффективности отраслей, таких как выпуск продукции, занятость и темпы роста. В отличие от большинства исследований, сосредоточенных на совокупном влиянии ПИИ на ВВП, наша работа является новаторской благодаря отраслевому подходу. Результаты показывают, что иностранные инвестиции значительно способствовали развитию промышленности и расширению сферы услуг, особенно в транспорте и логистике, туризме и ИКТ. В сельском хозяйстве ПИИ обеспечили стабильный, но умеренный рост. Эконометрические результаты подтверждают положительную корреляцию ПИИ с занятостью и выпуском продукции, хотя степень воздействия различается по секторам. Исследование предоставляет эмпирические доказательства и практические рекомендации для совершенствования инвестиционной политики по секторам с целью укрепления долгосрочного экономического развития Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: Прямые иностранные инвестиции (ПИИ), экономический рост, Узбекистан, сельское хозяйство, промышленность, сфера услуг, межотраслевая аналитика, занятость, ВВП, отраслевое воздействие.

INTRODUCTION

In the process of globalization, foreign investments are considered as an important factor of economic growth and development. In particular, through foreign direct investment (FDI), new technologies, management experience and financial resources are entering the economy of countries. This serves to improve production efficiency and strengthen competitiveness.

For example, China has attracted large-scale FDI since the 1980s to develop its manufacturing industry. This process turned the country into a global manufacturing center and contributed greatly to its economic growth. Singapore has become a leading financial center in the region, actively using FDI to develop the high-tech and financial services sectors. Vietnam has increased its export potential and diversified its economy in recent years by attracting FDI to develop the textile and electronics industries. And India has gained an important place in the global IT services market by attracting FDI in information technology and telecommunication sectors. These examples show successful experiences of FDI in developing different sectors in different countries. FDI inflows to the OECD area increased by 80%, but this was mainly the result of an increase in large investments in the Netherlands. Excluding FDI flows received by Luxembourg and the Netherlands, which have been highly volatile in recent years, OECD FDI flows fell by 14%. The flow of direct investments to non-OECD G20 countries decreased by 19%. The main reason for this is geopolitical risk and economic policy uncertainty affecting the confidence of foreign investors in the People's Republic of China.

In 2023, foreign investments and loans attracted to the main capital of Uzbekistan accounted for 56,7% of total investments. This is the highest indicator in the last 20 years and shows the growing interest of international investors in the country's economy. In January-October 2024, industrial products worth 18766,2 billion sums were produced by enterprises with foreign investments in Tashkent region. It is 17,2 percent of the total production, which confirms the importance of foreign investments in the industrial sector. The number of foreign-invested enterprises in Uzbekistan is increasing year by year. For example, in 2019, the number of such enterprises was 9,642, and in 2022, this indicator reached 14,993. This indicates that the investment environment in the country is improving. In 2013, the value of FDI amounted to 691 million dollars, and by 2023 this value will exceed 2 billion dollars.

According to the Central Bank, in the first half of 2024, the volume of foreign direct investment (FDI) increased 2.5 times. In January-June, the volume of decentralized investments in the economy of Uzbekistan increased by 38.7%, and this contributed to the growth of total investments by 32.7%. In the first half of the year, foreign direct investments worth 5.32 billion dollars were attracted. However, in the second quarter, the volume of investments began to stagnate. Compared to the same period in 2023, the ratio of foreign direct investment to the gross domestic product increased from 6 percent to 12 percent. The share of added value in GDP is 22,9%, and the level of employment in this sector is 25%. As for the industrial sector, the share of added value in GDP has increased by 9% over the last 10 years, and the employment rate is 24,1%. In addition, today the most developing sector is the service sector. Services such as transportation and logistics, tourism, and ICT are the sectors attracting the most investment. Therefore, the employment rate in the service sector is 50%.

The research has 3 objectives. The main goal of this study is to analyze the trends and patterns of FDI in key sectors of Uzbekistan over the years. Through this analysis, we can see which sector attracted more FDI, then the impact of FDI can be determined. The next aim of this research is to evaluate the effectiveness

of FDI on sectoral output such as, agriculture, industry, and services. By this way, we determine which sector contributes to economic growth by attracting FDI. Then we aimed to determine the correlation between GDP and economic indicators such as sectoral annual growth and employment rates. Econometric analysis helps us to determine the relationship between variables. For example, does attracting FDI increase the level of employment or annual growth in sectors? At the same time, we will evaluate each indicator. Our novelty is to study, while most researchers analyze the impact of FDI on total GDP, we want to do a cross-sectoral analysis. Our sectors include agriculture, industry and services. We also obtain separate results for each sector in our research. Our time series data includes the last 27 years of data on 3 sectors from 1997 to 2023.

Our research will consist of background information about global and Uzbekistan's FDI volume, literature review, methodology, results and discussion, conclusions and recommendations. In the literature review, there will be detailed information about the differences between the previous researchers' analysis, the research gap and the difference between our research. In the methodology section, we provide information about the techniques and models we use. In the Results section, we describe the new econometric results in detail. Finally, we will summarize and give some suggestions for policymakers.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

In recent years, the study of the impact of FDI on the economy of Uzbekistan has gained considerable attention among researchers [1,7]. While some researchers tried to find ways to increase the volume of FDI to the economy [6,8], others analyzed FDI, its sectoral contribution and employment in their studies [2,3].

Khoshimov J. [8] identified ways to attract foreign investments to Uzbekistan and presented the existing issues in this area. Based on his recommendations, it is possible to gain insights into the problems that could hinder future economic development. Imomkulov T.B. [7] conducted research on the growth rate of FDI and its impact on income and the institutional environment. He also studied developing countries alongside Uzbekistan. FDI affects not only economic sectors but also small businesses. Numonjonova N.A [5] has also described investment as a key factor in the development of small businesses. In her research, she provided recommendations on how to direct FDI for business development by utilizing foreign experiences. In his study, Balbaa M. [4] demonstrated in detail the role of FDI in the development of the digital economy. Through his analysis covering the period from 2005 to 2022, it is possible to examine FDI's contribution to technological advancement and its impact on the expansion of the digital economy. FDI affects the development of various sectors differently. On this topic Dašić B., Trklja R., Savić M. [3], in their research, conducted a comparative analysis of the manufacturing and services sectors using examples from several countries. Kler R., Gulyamov N.B., Supiev R. [2] aimed to assess contribution of FDI to employment in different sectors during the period from 2017 to 2022.

Kler et al. [2] used panel data for their research study. For econometric analysis, they applied the PCSEs Model and Random Effects Models and compared the results. Kobilov et al. [1] used data on Foreign Direct Investment, Domestic Investment, and Economic Growth for the period 2010–2019 in their research. In the results section, they conducted the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test for Unit Root, Co integration test, VECM Results, and Granger Causality Wald Tests, interpreting the results. This proved the statistical significance of their research. Balbaa M. [4] conducted econometric analysis for the variables GDP, FDI inflows, and FDI outflows. He used time series data for the research and interpreted descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and the OLS model in the results section. In her research, Numonjonova N.A [5] mainly utilized theoretical data. She elaborated on the Classification of investment factors in small business, which helps to understand how FDI affects business and its efficiency from a theoretical perspective.

In conclusion, there are many studies in this field. However, many of them focus on general impact of FDI on GDP. We found research gap that researchers did not analyze 3 sectors together and compare. We selected three dominant sectors in Uzbekistan: agriculture, industry and services. There are reasons why we choose these sectors. Agriculture remains a dominant sector in Uzbekistan, contributing significantly to GDP. However, it faces challenges in modernization and technological advancement. FDI can play a pivotal role in enhancing productivity and adopting sustainable agricultural practices, which is critical for Uzbekistan's rural development. The industrial sector, particularly manufacturing, is key to Uzbekistan's economic diversification efforts. FDI in industry can boost productivity, introduce new technologies, and increase exports, making it a critical area for investment to promote economic growth. The services sector (including finance, education, healthcare, and IT) has grown rapidly in many developing economies. As Uzbekistan continues to modernize its economy, FDI in services can help drive digital transformation and enhance the quality of life by improving access to services and infrastructure.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Our primary objective in this research is to determine which sector's development through the attraction of FDI would further enhance our economy and to provide scientific evidence for this. Unlike previous studies, we have selected the agriculture, industry, and service sectors to analyze how their growth rates and employment levels within these sectors impact our economy and to what extent.

For the analysis, we have chosen data from the period 1997–2023 and aim to conduct correlation, regression, and stationarity tests among the variables. All our data has been collected from the World Bank Open Data website.

Our dependent variable is GDP growth, while the independent variables are FDI, Industry growth, Employment in Industry, Agriculture growth, Services growth, and Employment in Services.

Our mathematical model consists of the following:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6)$$

Y – dependent variable

X – independent variable

According to our research function form will be:

$$GDPG = f(\text{FDI, Industry growth, Emp Industry, Agriculture growth, Services growth, Emp services})$$

GDPG refers specifically to the increase in a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) over time. GDP measures the total value of goods and services produced within a country in a given period and is often used as a key indicator of economic performance. The study also considers FDI (Foreign Direct Investment) is capital investment made by foreign companies or investors in a specific sector of a country's economy. Industry Growth is the growth rate of production or economic activity in the industrial sector. Employment in Industry is the share of the working-age population employed in the industrial sector. Agriculture Growth is the annual growth rate of production or economic activity in the agricultural sector. Services Growth is the growth rate of economic activity or production in the services sector. Employment in Services is the share of the working-age population employed in the services sector.

The final panel data econometric model becomes as follows.

$$GDPG = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ FDI} + \beta_2 \text{ Industry growth} + \beta_3 \text{ Emp Industry} + \beta_4 \text{ Agriculture growth} + \beta_5 \text{ Services growth} + \beta_6 \text{ Emp services} + \mu$$

In the above model, GDPG is the dependent variable we try to explain or predict.

Here is β - coefficient parameters. These coefficients represent the long-run effects of various independent variables on GDPG and μ -error term, which captures the unexplained variation in economic growth not accounted for by the independent variables in the model.

For analyzing correlation and regression relationship we have 2 hypotheses.

First is null hypothesis: variables are independent.

Second is alternative hypothesis: variables are dependent.

If our p value is less than 0.05 we reject H_0 and accept H_a hypothesis, then we test statistical significance level. We check effects of independent variables to dependent variables. If coefficients show “-” there is negative impact ($p < 0.05$) or they represent “+” there is positive relationship between variables ($p < 0.05$). If p value higher than 0.05, then we understand it does not significant impact and statistical insignificant.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This study aims to assess the impact of foreign investments on the economy of Uzbekistan by Cross-sectoral analysis, including agriculture, industry and service sectors. It also helps to find relationship between employment and sectors, their contributing to GDP growth of country. This section gives econometric analysis results, such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, Augmented Dicky Fuller test for checking stationarity and ARDL regression model outcomes.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GDPG	27	6.121	1.782	1.996	9.473
FDI	27	1.787	1.006	.543	3.843
Industry growth	27	6.723	4.675	1.778	26.069
Emp Industry	27	21.961	1.554	19.702	24.18
Agriculture growth	27	5.043	1.858	.266	8.334
Services growth	27	6.813	2.772	-.772	12.502
Emp services	26	47.483	3.383	40.121	50.895

Table 2. Matrix of correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
(1) GDPG	1.000						
(2) FDI	0.248	1.000					
(3) Industry_growth	0.523	0.436	1.000				
(4) Emp_Industry	0.256	0.689	0.452	1.000			
(5) Agriculture_gr~h	0.443	-0.288	0.048	-0.360	1.000		
(6) Services_growth	0.845	0.332	0.209	0.241	0.193	1.000	
(7) Emp_services	0.515	0.589	0.593	0.887	-0.071	0.357	1.000

Table 3. Checking for stationarity (ADF test results)

Variables	ADF	
	Level	1st-Difference
GDPG	-2.638*	-7.908***
FDI	-2.695*	-7.736***
Industry growth	-3.902***	-7.880***
Emp Industry	-0.416	-2.864**
Agriculture growth	-2.345	-5.854***
Services growth	-4.086***	-7.704***
Emp services	-3.603***	-3.409**

Table 4. ARDL regression model

ARDL(1,0,0,0,0,0,0) regression

Sample: 1998 - 2022,

but with a gap Number of obs = 24

 $F(7, 16) = 54.45$

Prob > F = 0.0000

R-squared = 0.9597

Adj R-squared = 0.9421

Root MSE = 0.0671

Log likelihood = 35.654086

	Coef.	Std.Err.	t	P>t	[95%Conf.	Interval]
log_GDPG						
FDI	-0.050	0.020	-2.490	0.024	-0.093	-0.007
log_Industry_growth	0.259	0.048	5.440	0.000	0.158	0.360
log_Emp_Industry	-1.616	0.637	-2.540	0.022	-2.966	-0.267
log_Agriculture_growth	0.053	0.023	2.270	0.037	0.003	0.102
log_Services_growth	0.526	0.054	9.770	0.000	0.412	0.640
log_Emp_services	1.482	0.788	1.880	0.078	-0.188	3.153
_cons	-0.354	1.710	-0.210	0.839	-3.979	3.271

Descriptive statistics

Table 1 displays the descriptive statistics of the data. The outcomes give information about value of Industry growth range from 1.778 to 26.069 which means that the variation of this variable is high in Uzbekistan's economy during the study period. Moreover, this table indicates the mean of GDPG, FDI, Industry growth, Employment in Industry, Agriculture growth, Services growth and Employment in Services are 6.121, 1.787, 6.723, 21.961, 5.043, 6.813 and 47.483, respectively.

Correlation analysis

Table 2 demonstrates that there is a positive relationship between GDP growth and all independent variables. The strongest correlation is observed between GDP growth and Services growth, amounting to 84%. This indicates that an increase in GDP growth is accompanied by an 85% increase in the services sector or vice versa.

However, according to this model, there is a weak positive correlation between GDP growth and the independent variables FDI and Employment in Industry, with correlation values of 24% and 25%, respectively.

Additionally, we can conclude that as the remaining independent variables—Agriculture growth, Industry growth, and Employment in Services—rise, GDP growth also increases, but at a slower rate. This is because the correlation values for these variables are 44%, 52%, and 51%, respectively.

Unit root test result

In Table 3, we observe that five of our independent variables—GDP growth, FDI, Industry growth, Services growth, and Employment in Services—are stationary at level. P value of GDPG and FDI is less than 0.10, while others $p < 0.01$. However, the remaining two variables, Employment in Industry and Agriculture growth, were found to be non-stationary.

To make these non-stationary variables stationary, we applied first-stage differencing. Conducting the stationarity test helped us determine the appropriate regression model for the analysis.

Since some variables have a unit root while others are stationary, we identified the ARDL model as the most suitable approach for our study.

Regression analysis

According to Table 4, number of observations is 24. F-statistic test result is 54.45 with a p-value of 0.0000, indicating that the overall model is statistically significant. R-squared outcome is 0.9597, meaning that approximately 96% of the variation in GDPG is explained by the model. The value of Root MSE is 0.0671, representing the model's standard error of the regression.

As shown in the table, the p-values for all independent variables are less than 0.10, indicating that they are statistically significant. FDI and Employment in Industry have a negative impact on GDP growth. This means that a 1-unit increase in FDI decreases GDP growth by 0.05 units, or if the number of workers in the industrial sector increases by 1 unit, GDP growth declines by 1.61%.

However, the growth of agriculture, industry, and services contributes positively to GDP growth. Notably, a 1% increase in employment in the services sector leads to a 1.48-unit increase in GDP growth.

Our study provides valuable insights into the relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI), sectoral growth, employment, and GDP growth in Uzbekistan over the period from 1997 to 2023. The findings reveal both positive and negative impacts of the independent variables on GDP growth, measured as the dependent variable.

Balbaa M. [4] found in his research positive relationship between GDP and FDI inflow, while our result shows negative relationship. This result unexpected, it may indicate that FDI inflows are concentrated in sectors or projects with delayed economic returns or that the economy lacks sufficient capacity to efficiently absorb foreign investments. This finding highlights the need for improved policies to better integrate FDI into the economy and ensure it contributes positively to economic growth.

Industry growth, on the other hand, shows a positive and highly significant impact on GDP growth. This underscores the critical role of industrial expansion in driving economic development. Promoting industrialization, modernizing production techniques, and investing in technology could yield substantial economic benefits. However, employment in the industrial sector exhibits a negative and significant impact on GDP growth. This result suggests inefficiencies or overreliance on labor-intensive practices, which may hinder productivity and limit the sector's contribution to economic growth.

Agriculture growth has a positive and statistically significant impact on GDP growth. Although its impact is relatively modest, this result emphasizes the importance of agriculture as a foundational sector in the economy. Modernization and increased investment in this sector could further enhance its contribution to GDP growth.

The services sector emerges as the most significant driver of GDP growth. This finding highlights the increasing importance of the services sector in Uzbekistan's economy, particularly in fostering diversification and resilience. Additionally, employment in the services sector has a significant positive impact on GDP growth which indicates that job creation in the services sector can play a critical role in accelerating economic growth.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

During our research to study the cross-sectoral impact of FDI on the Uzbek economy, we obtained several practical results. The results of this study show that foreign direct investment (FDI), sectoral growth, and employment levels have different impacts on the development of the Uzbek economy. In our study, we used correlation and regression analyses for econometric analysis to determine the importance of cross-sectoral FDI. In particular, it was found that FDI and employment in the industrial sector have a negative impact on economic growth. This situation can be explained by the inefficient placement of investments or the inability of the economy to fully absorb foreign investments.

However, the growth of the industrial, service, and agricultural sectors has a positive impact on GDP growth. In particular, the services sector stands out as the main driver of the economy. An increase in employment levels in the services sector significantly contributes to economic growth.

Policy recommendations

To ensure sustainable growth of the Uzbek economy, it is necessary to put forward several important policy recommendations. First of all, attention should be paid to increasing the efficiency of foreign investment. For this, it is important to direct FDI flows to sectors with high added value, create a favorable environment for foreign investors and reduce bureaucratic barriers. Secondly, it is necessary to implement technological modernization and training programs in the industrial sector. This will allow increasing labor productivity in the industry, introducing modern technologies and enhancing the positive impact on economic growth. Strategies should also be developed to develop the services sector. By encouraging innovation, accelerating digitalization, and supporting entrepreneurship in the services sector, this sector can be turned into a key driver of the economy. The implementation of these policy measures will accelerate the diversification process in the economy and ensure sustainable and long-term growth.

References

1. Kobilov A.E., Kurbonov O.A., Amirov A.M., Usmanova D.K., (2020) The Impact of Investment on the Economic Development of Uzbekistan. *Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(7), 2008-2015.
2. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343325007_The_Impact_of_Investment_on_the_Economic_Development_of_Uzbekistan
3. Kler R., Gulyamov N.B., Supiev R., (2024) Analyzing Uneven Distribution of Sectoral Employment in Uzbekistan Adopting Panel Data Approach. *FMDB Transactions on Sustainable Management Letters*, 2(1), 29-38.
4. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383282884_Analyzing_Uneven_Distribution_of_Sectoral_Employment_in_Uzbekistan_Adopting_Panel_Data_Approach
5. Dašić B., Trklja R., Savić M., (2019) Comparative analysis of inflows and sectoral distribution of the foreign direct investments flows. *Mining and Metallurgy Engineering Bor*, 1(2), 31-40.
6. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336426698_Comparative_analysis_of_inflows_and_sectoral_distribution_of_the_foreign_direct_investments_flows
7. Balbaa M., (2024) FDI and Digital Economic Growth: Analyzing The Role of Foreign Direct Investment in Fostering Digital Economic Development and Technological Progress in Uzbekistan. *International Finance and Accounting*, (5).
8. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385877690_FDI_AND_DIGITAL_ECONOMIC_GROWTH_ANALYZING_THE_ROLE_OF_FOREIGN_DIRECT_INVESTMENT_IN_FOSTERING_DIGITAL_ECONOMIC_DEVELOPMENT_AND_TECHNOLOGICAL_PROGRESS_IN_UZBEKISTAN
9. Numonjonova N.A., (2024) Investment - an Important Factor in the Development of Small Business. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 7(12), 1371-1379.
10. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/386895500_Investment_an_Important_Factor_in_the_Development_of_Small_Business
11. Jaliilov Sh.Z., Latipova Sh.M., (2018) Methods of Improving Foreign Investments in the Economy of Uzbekistan. *Innovative Technologies in Economy*, 5(17), 6-9.
12. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345132581_METHODS_OF_IMPROVING_FOREIGN_INVESTMENTS_IN_THE_ECONOMY_OF_UZBEKISTAN
13. Imomkulov T.B., (2023) The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth in Uzbekistan. *Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim*, 24(6), 28-33.
14. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377483661_THE_IMPACT_OF_FOREIGN_DIRECT_INVESTMENT_ON_ECONOMIC_GROWTH_IN_UZBEKISTAN
15. Khoshimov J., (2023) Ways to increase the Volume of Attracting Foreign Direct Investments to The Economy. *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 11(4), 93-99.

16. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374639941_WAYS_TO_INCREASE_THE_VOLUME_OF_ATTRACTING_FOREIGN_DIRECT_INVESTMENTS_TO_THE_ECONOMY
17. Ebghaei F., (2023) The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth in the MENA Region. *Izmir Journal of Economics*, 38(2), 321-335.
18. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/2486171>
19. De Mello L., (1999) Foreign direct investment – led growth: evidence from time series and panel data. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 5(1), 133 – 151.
20. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/5215559_Foreign_Direct_Investment-Led_Growth_Evidence_from_Time_Series_and_Panel_Data
21. Griffin K., (1970) Foreign Capital, Domestic Savings and Economic Development. *Bulletin of the Oxford University Institute of Economics & Statistics*, 32(2), 99 – 112.
22. Leff, N.H., (1969) Dependency Rates and Saving Rates. *American Economic Review*. New York: American Economic Association, 59(5).
23. Lessmann C., (2013) Foreign direct investment and regional inequality: A panel data analysis. *China Economic Review*, 24 (1) 129 – 149.
24. Mencinger J., (2003) Does Foreign Direct Investments Always Enhance Economic Growth *Kyklos*, Vol 56.
25. Metwally M. Tamaschke R., (1994) The interaction among foreign debt, capital flows and growth: Case studies. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 16(6) 597 – 608.
26. Noorbakhsh F., Paloni A., Youssef A., (2001) Human Capital and FDI Inflows to Developing Countries: New Empirical Evidence. *World Development*, 29(9) 1593 – 1610.
27. Pasmazoglou J., (1972) Growth, investment and saving ratios: Some long and medium-term associations by groups of countries. *Bulletin of the Oxford University Institute of Economics & Statistics*, 34(4) 309 – 328.
28. Rothgeb J., (1988) Direct foreign investment in mining and manufacturing in underdeveloped states. *The Social Science Journal*, 25 (1), 21 – 43.
29. Smits W.J.B., (1988). Foreign direct investment and export and import value – A cross – section study for thirty less developed countries. *The Economist*, 136 (1), 91 – 117.
30. Schneider P.H., (2005) International trade, economic growth and intellectual property rights: A panel data study of developed and developing countries. *Journal of Development Economics*, 78 (2), 529 – 547.
31. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/222627170_International_Trade_Economic_Growth_and_Intellectual_Property_Rights_A_Panel_Data_Study_of_Developed_and_Developing_Countries

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. № 10

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100